

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Potential donors for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

*R.K. Sahu, Plant Breeding Department,
IRRI*

Of 185 rice accessions from the Madhya Pradesh (India) germplasm collection screened at IRRI for resistance to BPH (standard seedbox screening technique), 18 were resistant.

Each seedling was infested with 7-10 second- to third-instar BPH biotype 1 nymphs at 7 d after seeding. Damage was scored on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 1-9 scale.

Aolesar, Jhili, and Banda were resistant. Akkalpom, Bhondu parewa, Cross 116, Dubraj, Dudga, Garrakath, Gathwan, Gobindbhog, Haruna dubraj, Hiranakhi, Jawphool, Aagyasal, Aagyasar, Assamchudi, and Makarkam were moderately resistant. Susceptible cultivars died 8-9 d after infestation.

Aolesar, Cross 116, Dudga, Haruma dubraj, Jhili, Aagyasal, and Aagyasar also are resistant to bacterial blight. □

Multiple resistance of BG367-3 to major insect pests and diseases

R. Saroja, M. Suriachandraselvan, N. Raju, and T. B. Ranganathan, Rice Research Station, Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

In the 1981 IRTP, BG367-3 (BG280-1-2/Ptb 33), a short-duration culture from Sri Lanka, was moderately resistant to rice leafhopper (LF) at IRRI and Tirur. From 1982 to 1986, BG367-3 was evaluated against other insect pests and diseases at Tirur.

BG367-3 was resistant to blast (BI) and moderately resistant to tungro (RTV), brown spot, gall midge, hispa,

between plants. The recommended 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha was applied.

IR32358-54-2-3-3 and IR32419-28-3-1-3 flowered the earliest, at 87 d after seeding (DAS) (see table). All other entries flowered 90-107 DAS; check CO 43 flowered 101 DAS. Ten lines yielded more than 6 t/ha.

Leaf yellowing due to RTV and soil problems caused very heavy damage to samba and thaladi crops in 1984. All

the test entries were exposed under field conditions and scored for leaf yellowing reaction. All IRRI lines were free from leaf yellowing and two lines showed resistance.

Entries IR32358-54-2-3-3 and IR28228-112-2-3-3-3 were susceptible to neck blast and IR31809-67-2-3 and IR32823-88-2-3 were susceptible to helminthosporiose. □

Yield performance of IRRI lines and their reactions to diseases.

Breeding line	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t/ha)	Helminthosporiose	Bacterial blight	Sheath rot	Grain discoloration
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2 (IR62)	94	7.4	3	3	3	1
IR32358-32-2-3-3	96	3.0	1	3	0	1
IR32358-54-2-3-3 ^a	86	3.2	1	3	3	1
IR32419-28-3-1-3	87	6.5	1	3	3	0
IR25604-99-1-3-2-2	94	3.7	3	0	3	3
IR25619-75-2-3-2-3	100	6.9	3	0	3	3
IR27313-67-1-2	98	8.6	5	1	3	1
IR27325-53-2	98	5.6	3	3	3	3
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	97	4.1	5	3	3	5
IR328224-3-2-3-2	97	4.1	3	5	3	3
IR28226-24-1-2-3-2	96	4.0	5	3	0	0
IR28228-96-3-2-1-3	99	4.2	5	3	3	3
IR28228-106-1-2-3-2	90	6.2	3	1	1	3
IR28228-112-2-3-3-3 ^a	95	4.2	5	3	1	3
IR28228-119-2-3-1-1	97	3.7	3	3	3	3
IR29519-116-2-2-2	91	5.4	3	3	1	1
IR29519-135-3-3-2	101	6.0	3	1	0	3
IR29519-157-1-2-1	91	3.0	5	5	3	3
IR29522-4-2-3	92	7.1	5	1	3	5
IR29668-34-1-1-2	103	3.8	3	1	3	3
IR29723-7-1-1-2	104	4.2	3	3	3	3
IR29723-143-3-2-1	107	4.0	5	5	1	3
IR29723-163-3-2-2	91	5.8	3	3	1	1
IR331805-20-1-3-3	91	6.1	3	5	3	1
IR31811-35-3-3-2	102	6.3	3	5	3	1
IR31827-80-3-3-2	102	2.1	3	3	3	3
IR31836-10-1-2-2	98	2.8	3	5	3	3
IR31836-42-1-3-2	101	5.2	5	3	3	3
IR31838-63-2-2-2	99	1.4	3	1	5	5
IR31855-69-1-2-3	91	4.4	3	3	3	3
IR31867-1-2-3-3	100	3.0	3	1	5	1
IR31867-4-3-3-3	101	4.9	5	3	3	3
IR31892-46-3-2 ^b	93	1.9	3	5	5	3
IR31901-17-1-2-2 ^b	103	1.8	3	3	5	3
IR31917-31-3-2-3	94	8.1	3	5	3	1
IR31917-96-3-3-1	105	5.4	5	3	3	3
IR31809-67-2-3	98	4.0	7	3	3	5
IR32822-36-1-3	98	3.1	5	3	3	1
IR32823-1-1-3	100	1.2	5	3	3	3
IR32823-22-1-3	104	2.2	3	3	3	3
IR32823-88-2-2	104	6.3	7	0	3	3
IR32830-23-2-2	101	2.1	3	3	5	5
IR32848-36-2-2	102	2.0	3	1	1	1
IR33059-120-2-1	103	2.0	5	5	3	3
IR34583-38-3	102	3.8	3	1	3	3
CO 43 ^a	101	4.8	3	3	5	3

^aAll entries scored 0 for blast except IR32358-54-2-3-3 and IR28228-112-2-3-3-3, which scored 7.

^bAll entries had a leaf yellowing score of 0 except IR31892-46-3-2 and IR31901-17-1-2-2, which scored 3. The check CO 43 scored 7.

Reaction of BG367-3 to major insect pests and diseases. Tirur, India, 1982-86.

Entry	Maturity (d)	Damage ^a											
		RTV	Bl	Brown spot	Sheath rot	Grain discoloration	Gall midge	Hispa	Green leafhopper	Stem borer		Yield LF (t/ha)	
										Deadheart	Whiteheads		
BG367-3	115	3	1	4	5	5	3	3	3	3	3	3	5.1
IR36	120	5	3	7	5	5	7	3	7	9	5	9	5.5
IR50	115	7	9	5	5	5	5	3	5	9	7	9	6.3
TKM9	115	8	9	5	5	5	5	3	9	9	7	9	5.6
ADT36	115	8	2	5	5	5	7	5	7	9	7	9	4.4
PY3	115	4	3	5	7	7	5	5	3	9	5	9	4.5
TN1 (susceptible check)	125	8	5	5	9	9	7	5	9	9	9	9	4.2

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice. 1-9 scale.

green leafhopper (GLH), and stem borers (SB) (see table). It has good yield potential.

The highly popular IR50 and TKM9 are severely damaged by Bl during

navarai (Dec-Apr). TKM9, recommended for sornavari (Apr-Aug), also was heavily damaged by RTV in 1984-85. IR50 is highly susceptible to LF and SB in early

samba (Jul-Nov).

BG367-3 is now under multilocation trials in Tamil Nadu and is being used in breeding for insect and disease resistance at Tirur. □

Resistance of IR varieties to leafhoppers and planthoppers

R. Velusamy, R. Rajendran, and P.C. Sundara Babu, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India; and G.S. Khush, Plant Breeding Department, IIRI

We evaluated 25 IR varieties for resistance to rice green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*. Pregerminated seeds were sown in rows in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with Ptb 33 as the resistant check and TN1 the susceptible check. Each variety had five replications. At 7 d after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 20 per variety and infested with 7-8 1st-instar nymphs of BPH and WBPH and 5 2d-instar GLH nymphs per seedling. When the susceptible check died, test varieties were rated for damage by the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)*.

Levels of resistance to GLH, BPH, and WBPH differed significantly. IR62 and IR64 exhibited high resistance to all three hopper species (see table). IR28, IR52, IR54, IR56, IR58, IR62,

Reactions of IR varieties to leafhoppers and planthoppers.

Variety	Damage rating ^a					
	GLH		BPH		WBPH	
IR5	6.6	e	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR8	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR20	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR22	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR24	5.4	d	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR26	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR28	1.0	a	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR29	6.2	e	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR30	5.4	d	9.0	f	6.2	d
IR32	3.4	c	9.0	f	5.4	d
IR34	3.0	bc	9.0	f	5.4	d
IR36	2.6	b	6.6	e	5.0	c
IR38	5.4	d	9.0	f	6.6	e
IR40	6.6	e	6.6	e	6.6	e
IR42	2.6	b	5.2	d	5.0	c
IR46	6.6	e	4.6	c	5.4	d
IR48	2.6	b	3.4	b	3.0	b
IR50	3.4	c	9.0	f	9.0	f
IR52	1.0	a	2.6	b	1.4	a
IR54	1.0	a	6.6	e	2.6	b
IR56	1.4	a	3.4	b	2.6	b
IR58	1.0	a	5.4	d	3.4	b
IR60	3.4	c	5.4	d	5.4	d
IR62	1.0	a	1.4	a	1.4	a
IR64	1.0	a	1.0	a	1.0	a
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	1.0	a	1.0	a	1.0	a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.0	f	9.0	f	9.0	f

^aMean of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. Damage rating is based on the SES 0-9 scale.

and IR64 were highly resistant to GLH; IR5, IR36, IR42, IR46, and

IR60 were moderately resistant to all three species. □